

Einstein's 1917 Universe Model and the Origin of the Cosmological Constant

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Abstract: This article explores Newton's cosmological assumptions and the resulting paradoxes, the origin of the cosmological constant, the shift from infinitely large to finite-sized models of the universe, and Einstein's 1917 model of the universe, which marks the first example and the beginning of relativistic cosmology.

Introduction

It is thought-provoking how equilibrium can arise in a finite-sized universe where there is only an attractive force between masses. Over time, one would expect all objects to draw closer, eventually merging into a single central mass. This paradox led Isaac Newton (1643-1727) to postulate an infinitely large universe, which led to the emergence of incompatibilities between Newton's cosmology and laws. Since the late 19th century, scientists and mathematicians have sought alternative solutions to these challenging issues. Einstein proposed a solution to these problems in the universe model he presented in 1917 based on his General Theory of Relativity (GTR). To make this solution possible, the “cosmological constant” was introduced for the first time as a mathematically defined parameter in the equations. This model embodies the problems and solutions of the previous period, as well as some of the basic concepts of modern cosmology. It symbolizes a conceptual shift from an infinitely large to a finite-sized universe, marking a significant leap forward and the beginning of modern cosmology.

The first section of this study explores Newton's cosmological assumptions, while the second section examines the paradoxes arising in Newtonian cosmology and the proposed solutions. In the third section, the origin of the cosmological constant and Einstein's basic cosmological assumptions are discussed, and in the fourth section,

Einstein's 1917 model of the universe is explained. The fifth section addresses the challenges associated with Einstein's model.

1. Newton's Cosmological Assumptions

Newton's law of gravitation only has attractive properties. In a universe where only, an attractive force exists between the masses, one would expect it to lose its stability and collapse upon itself. In contrast, observational data showed that the universe was remarkably stable and balanced. After publishing "*Principia* [21]" in 1687, Newton corresponded with Richard Bentley, a priest who sought to explain Newton's theories to his audience to refute atheism, between 1692 and 1693.¹ Bentley asked Newton how the universe remained in equilibrium under the influence of gravity. In response, Newton proposed the following solution in his letter dated December 10, 1692:

"...if the matter of our Sun & Planets & all the matter in the universe was evenly scattered throughout all the heavens, & every particle had an innate gravity towards all the rest & the whole space throughout which this matter was scattered, was but finite: the matter on the outside of this space would by its gravity tend towards all the matter on the inside & by consequence fall down to the middle of the whole space & there compose one great spherical mass. But if the matter was evenly diffused through an infinite space, it would never convene into one mass but some of it convene into one mass & some into another so as to make an infinite number of great masses scattered at great distances from one another throughout all that infinite space." [22]

In this passage, Newton first defined the problem and then proposed a solution based on the following three basic assumptions: First, that space is infinitely large; second, that the amount of matter is infinite; and third, that this infinite matter is uniformly (homogeneously) distributed throughout this infinitely large space.

¹ There were four exchanges of letters between Newton and Bentley between December 1692 and February 1693. These can be found at reference [20, pp. 94-105] and on <https://www.newtonproject.ox.ac.uk/> website.

According to Newton's reasoning, any particle of matter would be pulled equally in all directions by an infinite gravitational force, with opposing forces balancing each other out. However, this solution involved a deduction that could lead to mathematical issues, such as subtracting infinity from infinity and leaving zero.

Bentley, uneasy with the idea of an infinitely large universe, continued to explore the concept of infinity. Newton, aware of the potential paradoxes associated with infinity, addressed these concerns in his third and fourth letters but did not offer any new alternative solution beyond his original proposal. Despite Newton's insistence on this solution, as will be explained in Sections 2 and 3, analyses from the late 19th century onward revealed that Newton's law of gravitation and his cosmological assumptions were incompatible.

In modern mathematics, “infinity” is not considered a number, so calculations like “infinity minus infinity” are invalid and undefined. Assuming the result of such a calculation is zero or any specific number can lead to inconsistencies, contradictions, or paradoxes. The issue arises because, while gravitational force decreases in proportion to the square of the distance, the mass contributing to gravity in a homogeneous universe increases in direct proportion to the square of the distance. This implies that in an infinitely large universe where matter is homogeneously distributed in space, the gravitational force on any test mass would involve an “indeterminacy” due to the “infinity minus infinity” operation.

As will be explained in detail in Section 3, Einstein addressed this issue using gravitational field lines, interpreting it not as an “indeterminacy” problem but as a “divergence” problem. Around the same time, in his book *Introduction to Theoretical Physics*, Arthur Haas (1884-1941) described the problem using imaginary spheres, demonstrating that it would lead to a “divergence” or “indeterminacy” issue [\[17, pp. 445-446\]](#). A modern discussion of the problem can also be found in Alan Guth's *The Inflationary Universe* [\[16, p. 37; p. 295\]](#).

2. Problems and Solution Suggestions Between Newton's Cosmological Assumptions and Laws

Newton's fame helped popularize his cosmology throughout the 18th and 19th centuries. The idea that the universe is eternal (without a beginning) was also incorporated into Newtonian cosmology. Over time, it became apparent that this cosmology, which assumes an infinite amount of matter, space, and time, contained paradoxes. The most famous of these is the "Olbers paradox," popularized by Heinrich Wilhelm Olbers (1758-1840) in 1826.²

The apparent brightness of stars decreases in direct proportion to the square of the distance. However, in a homogeneous universe, the number of stars increases in proportion to the square of the distance. In an eternal universe with an infinite number of stars of infinite size, there should be an infinite number of stars in each line of sight. Therefore, an infinite amount of light must reach the observer from all directions.³ However, since the stars partially obscure each other, each line of sight should end at the surface of a star, and the sky should appear as bright as the surface of the Sun, leaving no dark areas. Thus, Olbers' Paradox states that in an eternal Newtonian universe, the sky must appear as bright as the surface of the Sun. At this point, Olbers raises the question: why does the concept of night exist? Why can't we see the entire sky as bright as the Sun's surface? The paradox suggests that at least one of the initial assumptions must be incorrect.⁴ This paradox explained by Olbers has significantly influenced thinkers in understanding the large-scale structure of the universe.

Deeper mathematical analysis of the problems awaited the development of the concepts and mathematics underpinning electromagnetic theory. When Newton's laws

² Although this paradox was known before Olbers, it became famous with Olbers' presentation.

³ Taking the integral for the total radiant energy density throughout all space, the integral diverges [\[46, pp. 611-612\]](#).

⁴ Olbers predicted the problem would be solved if gas and dust clouds in space absorbed light. However, this solution is flawed because these clouds increase in temperature as they absorb light energy. Once they reach thermal equilibrium, they re-emit this energy back into their surroundings through blackbody radiation. As theories of light and thermodynamics developed, scientists better understood these flaws and subsequently rejected Olbers' solution.

were reinterpreted using these new concepts and advanced mathematics, the nature of the problems that arose became clearer. In this context, Hugo von Seeliger (1849-1924) discussed the issues stemming from the incompatibility between Newton's laws and his cosmological assumptions in the 1890s [\[36-39\]](#).⁵ After completing his mathematical analysis, Seeliger described the problem in mechanics as follows:

"... According to the theory of the potential, consequently, *infinitely great accelerations must occur in the universe*, and this would be true with *any conceivable mode of mass distribution whatever*. There would therefore, result motions which, starting from finite velocities, would lead within a finite time, to infinite velocities. This conclusion contains within itself either an absurdity, or a direct contradiction of the theory of mechanics.

It seems that such doubts concerning the absolute correctness of the Newtonian law as those adduced here are always received with suspicion and distrust, even though it is impossible to produce anything demonstrable against them. Probably the reason for this is to be attributed in part, at least, to the difficulty with which people make clear to their minds that Newton's formula, despite its unbounded success in explaining astronomical facts, is and can be nothing more than an empirical law ..." [\[39, p. 546\]](#)

In summary, Seeliger argued that in an infinitely large universe where Newton's law of gravity holds, and an infinite amount of matter exists, infinitely large accelerations and velocities are possible, a result that is unacceptable in mechanics. Seeliger's paradox, as explained above, can also be understood as the divergence of the "gravitational potential" in an infinitely large universe with an infinite amount of matter. Like Olbers' paradox, Seeliger's paradox suggests that at least one of the initial assumptions must be incorrect.

According to Seeliger, the solution to this problem would require a modification of Newton's law of gravitation. Therefore, in the lines above, Seeliger stated that Newton's law is empirical and suggested that another law, consistent with

⁵ As Seeliger notes, this topic was addressed by mathematician Carl Neumann (1832-1925) before him [\[38\]](#). However, it was Seeliger's work that popularized the topic among scientists.

observational data and free of paradoxes, could serve the same function. He then made the following comments:

“But, since the Newtonian law is nothing more than a formula, derived purely empirically, which, within narrowly limited portions of space, furnishes a high degree of approximation to the facts of observation, any other formula, which does the same service may replace it, in case this substitution is recommended by other scientific considerations.” [\[39, p. 547\]](#)

Since Seeliger wanted to solve the problem without compromising the assumptions that the universe is infinitely large and that an infinite amount of matter is homogeneously distributed throughout the universe, he evaluated alternative solution scenarios that modified Newton's law of gravitation. To this end, he focused on solutions that attenuate the gravitational interaction to avoid the emergence of paradoxes. In his paper, Seeliger evaluated the proposals of Neumann and Hall for alternative modifications⁶ to Newton's law of gravitation and then proposed his own solution⁷ as follows:

$$F = G \frac{m_1 m_2 e^{-\lambda r}}{r^2}$$

Where:

F is the gravitational force between the two objects.

G is the gravitational constant.

m_1, m_2 are the masses of the two objects.

r is the separation between the centers of the objects.

λ is a mathematically defined constant.

In his solution, Seeliger proposed modifying Newton's gravitational law by multiplying it with the function $e^{-\lambda r}$. When λ equals zero, Seeliger's and Newton's formulas are identical. When λ takes a value greater than zero, Seeliger's formula attenuates the Newtonian gravitational force, preventing the gravitational potential

⁶ Seeliger critiqued Carl Neumann's solution, noting that while it addresses the issue of infinite potential, it does not offer significant practical advantages over Newton's original law. Similarly, A. Hall proposed another modification to Newton's law of gravity, but Seeliger also found it unsatisfactory [\[39, p. 549\]](#).

⁷ Seeliger's proposal to replace Newton's gravitational formula with this new formula had already been considered by Laplace (1749-1827), as Seeliger noted [\[39, pp. 548-549\]](#).

from diverging, thereby avoiding Seeliger's paradox. Seeliger then attempted to determine the value of λ based on observational data. Newton deduced Kepler's laws from his own, successfully explaining the elliptical orbits of the planets observed in his time. In the 17th and 18th centuries, the observed motions of the planets in the Solar System were consistent with Newton's laws. About a century later, William Herschel (1738-1822) showed that the motions of binary stars also obeyed the same laws [\[47, p. 16\]](#). These observations indicated that if Seeliger's modified formula was correct, the value of the parameter λ had to be very small. Such small values of λ were consistent with observational data, making the modification meaningful only at very long distances and effectively preventing paradoxes from arising.

Planets orbit the Sun in elliptical paths, and the point where a planet is closest to the Sun (perihelion) gradually shifts over time. This shift, known as "precession," affects all planets, including Mercury. Until the mid-19th century, this precession was thought to have been fully explained by Newton's theories. However, in 1845, astronomer Urbain Le Verrier (1811-1877) discovered a discrepancy of 43 arc seconds per century between Newton's predictions and the observed precession of Mercury's perihelion [\[17, p. 444\]](#). To reconcile this difference, scientists hypothesized the existence of an unobserved planet exerting a gravitational influence on Mercury's orbit, but no such planet was found despite extensive searches.

One proposed solution to the discrepancy between the predictions of Newton's theories and observational data was to revise Newton's law of gravitation, an idea that particularly interested Seeliger. He argued that, in addition to resolving the paradoxes mentioned above, any new law of gravitation should also account for the precession of Mercury's perihelion, which Newton's theories had failed to explain. Seeliger concluded his paper by testing the alternative gravitational laws proposed of his time against Mercury's observed motion [\[39, pp. 550-551\]](#). However, by the end of the 19th century, no alternative gravitation law, including Seeliger's own proposal, could explain Mercury's different motion.

Seeliger's work attracted attention, prompting mathematicians and scientists to propose various solutions to reconcile Newton's law of gravitation with his cosmological assumptions. These proposals included modifications to the law of gravitation, changes to the concept of mass (such as introducing negative mass),

different suggestions for the distribution of matter in the universe, and many more. As a detailed exploration of these alternative ideas is beyond the scope of this study, they will not be covered here. Still, interested readers can find further information on the alternatives from that period in Norton's article [\[28\]](#).

3. The Origin of the Cosmological Constant and Einstein's Basic Cosmological Assumptions

From the 17th century until 1916, when Einstein developed the basic assumptions of his universe model, the problem of how a finite-sized universe with only an attractive force between masses could stay stable remained unsolved. Consequently, the scientific community largely accepted Newton's concept of an infinite universe. During this long period, the idea of an infinitely large universe dominated the scientific community's perception of cosmology, leaving the notion of a finite-sized universe underexplored and largely undiscussed. Efforts to resolve the tension between Newton's laws and cosmological assumptions continued into the early 20th century and had matured considerably by the time Einstein announced the General Theory of Relativity (GTR) in November 1915 [\[5\]](#). Einstein's 1917 paper [\[1\]](#), where he presented his universe model, offered a solution to this tension.

Einstein also discussed the same issue in his book "*The Special and General Theory of Relativity* [\[8\]](#)" published in the same period. In the section titled "Cosmological Difficulties of Newton's Theory," Einstein addressed issues concerning the large-scale structure of the universe initially highlighted by Seeliger [\[8, pp. 125-127\]](#). He pointed out that in an infinite, homogeneous distribution of matter, the gravitational potential theoretically becomes infinite. Einstein noted that the number of gravitational force lines entering an imaginary sphere with a given test mass at its center would increase towards infinity as the sphere's diameter increases. He considered the problem arising from the "infinity minus infinity" operation in Newtonian cosmology as a problem of "divergence of the gravitational potential."

Einstein had analyzed Newton's theories, cosmology, and problems extremely well. Before presenting his own solution, he showed the original problem of Newtonian cosmology within the framework of two alternative cosmological scenarios. Within these scenarios, he attempted to solve the problems using the pre-GTR theoretical

structure. He then evaluated the issues within the framework of GTR by establishing analogical relationships. The details of these issues are analyzed in the following lines.

Einstein shared Seeliger's views, believing, like Seeliger, that the problem could be resolved with a new theory of gravitation. After announcing his General Theory of Relativity in November 1915, he, in the spirit of the times, compared his theory's predictions with Mercury's observed motion and found perfect agreement [3]: [4]. The new theory had successfully passed this test. For the first time, a theory of gravitation was able to fully explain Mercury's motion, and Einstein presented this success as an experimental confirmation of his theory [8, pp. 148-152]. Physicists are typically skeptical of new theories, and it can take considerable time for them to gain confidence. However, this achievement accelerated the widespread acceptance of GTR. Following this, Einstein began developing a new universe model based on GTR. His primary motivation was to determine whether the issues between Newton's law of gravitation and cosmology could be resolved within a GTR-based model. A new universe model grounded in GTR would serve as both a new test for GTR and, if successful, a significant theoretical achievement. After announcing GTR in November 1915, Einstein continued his cosmological studies for 15 months, ultimately publishing his findings in February 1917.

Einstein's 1917 paper, which explains his model of the universe, consists of an introduction and five sections [1]. The introduction and the first section focus on Newton's theories [1, pp. 142-144]. In the second section, Einstein attempted to determine the boundary conditions at infinity under the assumption of an infinitely large universe [1, pp. 144-148]. The primary purpose of these sections is to provide rational justifications for Einstein's fundamental assumptions, given that similar issues encountered in Newton's theories could potentially arise in Einstein's as well.

Einstein considered both finite and infinitely large universes within the GTR framework when developing his universe model. Like Newton, he was unable to develop a finite-sized model using the original GTR equations he had presented in 1915. Einstein expressed this situation as follows:

“...So, if it were certain that the field equations I have used so far (13)⁸ were the only ones compatible with the postulate of general relativity, we should probably conclude that the theory of relativity does not allow the hypothesis of a spatially finite universe.”⁹ [\[1, pp. 150-151\]](#)

Einstein also analyzed the model of an infinitely large universe within the framework of GTR. Therefore, the second section of his 1917 paper was devoted to determining the “boundary conditions” at infinity, assuming a universe of infinite size. However, he encountered significant challenges and ultimately did not succeed. Einstein made the following statements in his paper:

“...It is clear from what has been said so far that I have not succeeded in setting up boundary conditions for the spatially infinite. Nevertheless, there is still a possibility of getting by without the waiver stated under b. If it were possible to regard the universe as a closed continuum according to its spatial extensions, then no such boundary conditions would be necessary at all. In the following it will be shown that both the general relativity requirement and the fact of low star speeds are compatible with the hypothesis of the spatial closure of the universe as a whole; However, in order to implement this idea, a generalizing modification of the gravitational field equations is required.”¹⁰ [\[1, p. 148\]](#)

⁸ Einstein refers to original GTR equations.

⁹ Translated by the author from the original text: “Wenn es also sicher wäre, daß die von mir bisher benutzten Feldgleichungen (13) die einzigen mit dem Postulat der allgemeinen Relativität vereinbaren wären, so müßten wir wohl schließen, daß die Relativitätstheorie die Hypothese von einer räumlichen Geschlossenheit der Welt nicht zulasse.” [\[1, pp. 150-151\]](#)

¹⁰ Translated by the author from the original text: “Es geht aus dem bisher Gesagten hervor, daß mir das Aufstellen von Grenzbedingungen für das räumlich Unendliche nicht gelungen ist. Trotzdem existiert noch eine Möglichkeit, ohne den unter b angegebenen Verzicht auszukommen. Wenn es nämlich möglich wäre, die Welt als ein nach seinen räumlichen Erstreckungen geschlossenes Kontinuum anzusehen, dann hätte man überhaupt keine derartigen Grenzbedingungen nötig. Im folgenden wird sich zeigen, daß sowohl die allgemeine Relativitätsforderung als auch die Tatsache der geringen Sternengeschwindigkeiten mit der Hypothese von der räumlichen Geschlossenheit des Weltganzen vereinbar ist; allerdings bedarf es für die Durchführung dieses Gedankens einer verallgemeinernden Modifikation der Feldgleichungen der Gravitation.” [\[1, pp. 148\]](#)

Unable to develop a model of the universe based on the assumption that the universe is both finite and infinite using the original GTR equations, Einstein modified the equations by introducing a new parameter (λ),¹¹ inspired by the second scenario discussed below.

In the first section of his 1917 paper, Einstein evaluated Newtonian theories under two different scenarios based on varying assumptions. In the first scenario, he assumed that Newton's law of gravitation is valid and that the universe is infinite but inhomogeneous, with mass density decreasing towards zero faster than $1/r^2$ as the distance "r" from the center increases. In this scenario, the problem presented by Seeliger and explained in the Chapter 2 is avoided by the fact that the density of matter rapidly diminishes as it moves away from the center. After analyzing the first scenario, Einstein made the following remarks:

"If Boltzmann's distribution law for gas molecules is applied to stars by comparing the stellar system to a gas in thermal equilibrium, it follows that the Newtonian star system cannot exist at all. This is because the finite potential difference between the center and the spatially infinite corresponds to a finite density ratio. A disappearance of density at infinity results in a disappearance of density at the center."¹² [\[1, p. 143\]](#)

In this scenario, Einstein treated stars as gas molecules and demonstrated that stars concentrated at the center would eventually disperse toward the periphery.

¹¹ In November 1915, Einstein announced his field equations as follows:

$$G_{\mu\nu} = -\kappa \left(T_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} T \right)$$

In February 1917, he made the following modification to his field equations due to cosmological concerns:

$$G_{\mu\nu} - \lambda g_{\mu\nu} = -\kappa \left(T_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} T \right) \text{ [\[1, pp. 150-151\]](#)}$$

In the new equations, when $\lambda = 0$ is chosen, the old equations are obtained. The reasons for this modification in the equations will be discussed throughout this section.

¹² Translated by the author from the original text: "Wendet man das BOLTZMANNsche Verteilungsgesetz für Gasmoleküle auf die Sterne an, indem man das Sternsystem mit einem Gase von stationärer Wärmebewegung vergleicht, so folgt, daß das Newtonsche Sternsystem überhaupt nicht existieren könne. Denn der endlichen Potentialdifferenz zwischen dem Mittelpunkt und dem räumlich Unendlichen entspricht ein endliches Verhältnis der Dichten. Ein Verschwinden der Dichte im Unendlichen zieht also ein Verschwinden der Dichte im Mittelpunkt nach sich." [\[1, p. 143\]](#)

Finding this scenario unsuccessful, he concluded that Newton's law of gravitation required modification and moved on to evaluate the second scenario.

In the second scenario, in a model in which an infinite amount of matter is evenly distributed in the universe, he modified Newton's law of gravitation using Poisson's equations, with a parameter denoted by the symbol λ .¹³ By doing so, Einstein circumvented the issue highlighted by Seeliger explained in the second section, by attenuating the gravitational interaction, as Seeliger did. This approach aligned with Seeliger's preferred scenario.¹⁴ Einstein found this scenario successful and assessed it with the following statements:

“A universe like this would have no center with respect to the gravitational field. A decrease in density at spatial infinity would not have to be assumed, but both the average potential and the average density would remain constant up to infinity. The conflict with statistical mechanics noted in Newton's theory (first scenario) does not exist here.”¹⁵ [\[1, p. 144\]](#)

But Einstein also warned the reader not to take the method itself seriously with the following statements:

¹³ $\nabla^2\phi = 4\pi K\rho$; this equation, which Einstein used in his 1917 paper, is the representation of Newton's law of gravitation by Poisson's equation. In the second scenario, Einstein proposed a modification of Newton's law of gravitation using the equation: $\nabla^2\phi - \lambda\phi = 4\pi K\rho$ [\[1, p. 144\]](#). Einstein's proposed modification of Newton's law under this scenario is similar to Seeliger's proposed modification, but more like Carl Neumann's [\[27, p. 131\]](#); [\[28, p. 298\]](#). However, Einstein published this alternative without citing anyone. Einstein may not have cited anyone because he stated that this proposed solution should not be taken seriously, or he might have developed them independently.

¹⁴ Although Einstein's solution differs from Seeliger's, this difference is not important for the purposes of this study [\[27, p. 131\]](#); [\[28, p. 298\]](#).

¹⁵ Translated by the author from the original text: “Eine so beschaffene Welt hätte bezüglich des Gravitationsfeldes keinen Mittelpunkt. Ein Abnehmen der Dichte im räumlich Unendlichen müßte nicht angenommen werden, sondern es wäre sowohl das mittlere Potential als auch die mittlere Dichte bis ins Unendliche konstant. Der bei der NEWTONSchen Theorie konstatierte Konflikt mit der statistischen Mechanik ist hier nicht vorhanden.” [\[1, p. 144\]](#)

“We will first give you a way to do this, which in itself does not claim to be taken seriously: it only serves to make what follows stand out better.”¹⁶

[1, pp. 143-144]

It is puzzling that Einstein did not intend for the reader to take his method seriously in a scenario he favored, a decision that warrants deeper interpretation. Due to cosmological concerns, Newton's gravitational formula required modification despite its experimental success, and the same was true for GTR. Einstein's primary caution was to draw the reader's attention to the underlying conditions that necessitated adding a new parameter to the formula.

In the second section of his paper, Einstein eliminated the assumption that the universe is infinitely large, and in the third and fourth sections, he developed a finite and static model of the universe. To achieve this, he defined a new constant, denoted by the symbol " λ ", and modified GTR equations accordingly. For this purpose, Einstein established an analogical relationship between the modified Newtonian equation and the modified GTR equation and used the following expressions:

“However, the system of equations (14) (new GTR equations) allows an obvious extension that is compatible with the postulate of relativity, which is completely analogous to the extension of Poisson's equation given by equation (2) (Newton's modified gravity equation).”¹⁷ [1, p. 151]

Although Einstein established an analogical relationship between the Poisson equation modified by the parameter λ and the GTR equations modified by the parameter λ , the role and function of λ in these equations differ, since these two equations are functional in two different models of the universe. In the Poisson equation (Newton's modified gravity equation), λ attenuates the gravitational interaction in a model where an infinite amount of matter is homogeneously distributed

¹⁶ Translated by the author from the original text: "Wir geben hierfür zunächst einen Weg an der an sich nicht beansprucht, ernst genommen zu werden: er dient nur dazu, das Folgende besser hervortreten zu lassen." [1, pp. 143-144]

¹⁷ Translated by the author from the original text: "Das Gleichungssystem (14) erlaubt jedoch eine naheliegende, mit dem Relativitätspostulat vereinbare Erweiterung, welche der durch Gleichung (2) gegebenen Erweiterung der Poissonschen Gleichung voll kommen analog ist." [1, p. 151]

across an infinitely large universe. In contrast, within the GTR equations, λ serves to maintain equilibrium by counteracting gravity, effectively acting as a form of anti-gravity in a finite, static universe where matter is homogeneously distributed. Drawing an analogy between these two distinct equations, modified by the parameter λ with different functional properties further increases the confusion.

Einstein's main goal was to solve the same problem within the framework of two different theories. This problem arises from the question: "How can the observed stability occur in a universe where there is only an attractive force?" Considering this question, Newton could not find a solution other than assuming that the universe was infinitely large. However, this led to the emergence of paradoxes. To avoid paradoxes, Newton's gravitational formula had to be modified with the parameter, λ . Similarly, Einstein, unable to find a satisfactory solution, was compelled to modify GTR equations with the parameter λ . But what is the empirical evidence for the existence of λ , which appears only in the course of theoretical problems and attempts to solve them? Einstein had no answer to this question. In my view, if Einstein had empirical evidence for the existence of λ , the first and second sections of his 1917 paper would not have existed. Instead, he would have rationally justified the existence of λ based on experimental data. Einstein was uneasy about λ , which he defined mathematically and appeared to be an ad-hoc hypothesis. In 1917, Einstein had only theoretical problems and their solutions to help free the parameter λ from appearing as an ad-hoc hypothesis. Thus, Einstein sought to demonstrate that the introduction of λ into Newtonian theory was driven by rational necessity. By drawing an analogical relationship, he aimed to show that a similar necessity existed in his new theory. It is more accurate to consider the analogy Einstein established between the modifications as the similarity in the conditions that necessitated the change, rather than a similarity in the properties of the parameters themselves.

By using the modified GTR equations, Einstein successfully developed a finite-sized universe model, thereby eliminating the need to assume an infinitely large universe and avoiding the paradoxes associated with infinity. Therefore, for the first time, Einstein overcame the problem of how a finite universe, governed by gravity, could remain in equilibrium without collapsing in on itself, thanks to the introduction of the parameter λ . This new parameter, later known as the "cosmological constant,"

became one of the most significant concepts in modern cosmology. Einstein made a notable contribution to cosmology by liberating cosmological theories from the requirement of assuming infinitely large universes.

Models of the finite-sized universe have a long history dating back to the time of Plato and Aristotle (4th century BC). In the modern era, interest in finite-sized universe models increased after Bernhard Riemann (1826-1866), who developed spherical geometry. Based on Riemannian geometry, Karl Friedrich Zöllner (1834-1882) in 1872 proposed a closed, finite but unbounded universe with positive curvature. Another key figure was Karl Schwarzschild (1873-1916), who investigated the geometry of space and evaluated the conformity of physical space to hyperbolic and closed elliptic spaces. Despite their pioneering efforts, these early theories lacked empirical support and were often speculative in nature. They could not provide concrete evidence to substantiate their claims. Moreover, there was no comprehensive physical theory to relate non-Euclidean geometries to physical space. Therefore, until 1915, they were considered philosophical speculations with little acceptance among scientists, perceived as more mental exercises than valid scientific advancements. For those interested in further exploration, Helge Krogh's article, "*Geometry and Astronomy: Pre-Einstein Speculations of Non-Euclidean Space*"¹⁸ discusses other early attempts to relate non-Euclidean geometry to physical space, which are beyond the scope of this study. However, Einstein introduced his General Theory of Relativity in 1915, which provided a theoretical framework for such universe models. Inspired by these early examples, Einstein showed that it is possible to develop a finite universe model free of old paradoxes in a universe where gravitation exists. For these reasons, his GTR-based universe model represents an important milestone in the history of cosmology in the transition from infinite to finite-sized universe models.

While the gravitational interaction weakens in direct proportion to the square of the distance, the effect of the cosmological constant does not change with distance.

¹⁸ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1205.4909>

Therefore, as the distance increases, the effect of the cosmological constant increases relative to the effect of gravitational interaction. At the beginning of the 20th century, it was known, based on observational data, that the Solar System was not expanding or contracting but was highly stable. If the cosmological constant were set to a sufficiently large value, even the stability of the Solar System would be compromised, leading to its disintegration. Therefore, Einstein explained in his 1917 paper that the value of the cosmological constant must be very small to align with the observed stability of the Solar System.¹⁹

If the universe is finite in size, it can be static or dynamic. Whether the universe is static or dynamic can be understood depending on observational data. At the beginning of the 20th century, observational data on a universal scale had not matured, and most scientists believed the universe was limited to the Milky Way Galaxy.²⁰ The low speed of stars relative to the speed of light indicated that the universe, thought to consist only of the Milky Way, was extremely stable. Any viable cosmological theory needed to explain this observed stability. A static model of the universe could account for the apparent stability. This convinced Einstein to develop his model based on the assumption of a finite and static universe. Einstein made the following statements:

“The most important thing we know about the distribution of matter from experience is that the relative velocities of the stars are very small compared to the speed of light. I therefore believe that for the time being we may base our considerations on the following approximating assumption: There is a coordinate system relative to which matter can be regarded as permanently at rest.”²¹ [1, p. 148]

¹⁹ Einstein made the following statements: "If λ is sufficiently small, this field equation is also compatible with the empirical facts obtained from the solar system." Translated from the original text by the author: "Auch diese Feldgleichung ist bei genügend kleinem λ mit den am Sonnensystem erlangten Erfahrungstatsachen jedenfalls vereinbar." [1, p. 151]

²⁰ The concept of "galaxy" matured in the first quarter of the 20th century.

²¹ Translated from the original text by the author: "Das Wichtigste, was wir über die Verteilung der Materie aus der Erfahrung wissen, ist dies, daß die Relativgeschwindigkeiten der Sterne sehr klein sind gegenüber der Lichtgeschwindigkeit. Ich glaube deshalb, daß wir fürs erste folgende approximierende Annahme unserer

Einstein related the cosmological constant to the density of matter to ensure that his model remained static, as will be detailed in the next section. He used the cosmological constant not only to develop a finite universe model but also to make it static [\[1, p. 152\]](#). As the distance increases, the effect of the cosmological constant increases relative to the effect of gravitational interaction. In Einstein's static model of the universe, the main function of the cosmological constant is to counterbalance gravity's attractive force over long distances, preventing the universe from collapsing. Consequently, the value of the cosmological constant had to be carefully calibrated: small enough to maintain the stability of the Solar System, but large enough to offset gravity on a larger scale. Ultimately, Einstein employed the cosmological constant not only to develop a finite universe model but also to ensure its static nature [\[1, p. 152\]](#).

As explained above, the cosmological constant in Einstein's model serves to make the universe both finite and static. But how exactly does the cosmological constant achieve this? Addressing this question requires an understanding of its physical nature. In his 1917 paper, Einstein defined the cosmological constant solely through mathematical equations, without making any statements about its physical nature, and he never provided a clear explanation in later works either.²² Answering questions about the physical nature of the cosmological constant awaited the development of quantum theories, which is beyond the scope of this study.

4. Einstein's Finite and Static Model of the Universe

The previous section elaborated on the conditions and justifications behind Einstein's choices while constructing his model of the universe. In his 1917 paper, Einstein introduced his finite and stationary universe model in the third and fourth sections, following the establishment of his basic assumptions. To develop this model, he first needed to solve equations of the GTR. However, solving the field equations is practically impossible without making any predictions about the distribution of matter in the universe. Einstein regarded the concentration of matter in stars and stellar

Betrachtung zugrunde legen dürfen: Es gibt ein Koordinatensystem, relativ zu welchem die Materie als dauernd ruhend angesehen werden darf." [\[1, p. 148\]](#)

²² This topic is beyond the scope of the current study. Interested readers may check references: [\[30-31\]](#).

systems as minor irregularities, local deviations that can be ignored when considering the large-scale structure of the universe. At cosmological distances, he assumed that matter is uniformly distributed throughout the universe. Einstein used the following expressions in his 1917 paper:

“According to the general theory of relativity, the metric character (curvature) of the four-dimensional space-time continuum is determined at each point by the matter located there and its state. The metric structure of this continuum must therefore necessarily be an extremely intricate one because of the non-uniformity of the distribution of matter. However, if we are only focused on the structure on a large scale, we may consider the matter to be uniformly distributed over immense spaces, so that its distribution density becomes a tremendously slowly changing function. Thus, we proceed in a similar way to geodesists, who approximate the earth's surface, which is extremely complicated on a small scale, by an ellipsoid.”²³ [1, p. 148]

Einstein also assumed that matter moves slowly relative to the speed of light and does not exert pressure on its surroundings. These assumptions allowed him to simplify the energy-momentum tensor and solve the GTR equations accordingly.

Assuming that pressureless matter is uniformly distributed in space and using the cosmological constant, Einstein developed a finite and static yet unbounded model of the universe with a curved, closed, spherical geometry. Although his paper specifically references spherical geometry, the model is also compatible with the more general elliptical geometries, which include spherical geometry. The static nature of Einstein's universe model implies that the “curvature of space” or “radius of curvature

²³ Translated from the original text by the author: “Der metrische Charakter (Krümmung) des vierdimensionalen raumzeitlichen Kontinuums wird nach der allgemeinen Relativitätstheorie in jedem Punkte durch die daselbst befindliche Materie und deren Zustand bestimmt. Die metrische Struktur dieses Kontinuums muß daher wegen der Ungleichmäßigkeit der Verteilung der Materie notwendig eine äußerst verwickelte sein. Wenn es uns aber nur auf die Struktur im großen ankommt, dürfen wir uns die Materie als über ungeheure Räume gleichmäßig ausgebreitet vorstellen, so daß deren Verteilungsdichte eine ungeheuer langsam veränderliche Funktion wird. Wir gehen damit ähnlich vor wie etwa die Geodäten, welche die im kleinen äußerst kompliziert gestaltete Erdoberfläche durch ein Ellipsoid approximieren.” [1, p. 148]

(R)” remains constant over time. This curvature of space is calculated by the constant matter density and the cosmological constant, as expressed in the equations below.

$$\lambda = \kappa\rho/2 = 1/R^2$$

Where:

λ is the cosmological constant

ρ is the matter density

κ is the Einstein constant with a value $8\pi G/c^2$

R is the radius of curvature. [\[1, p. 152\]](#)

Due to the assumption of a static universe, the mass density and the cosmological constant, typically independent variables, become related, as demonstrated in the equation above. This relationship explains how the “radius of the universe (R)” remains constant over time. In Einstein's model, although the volume of space is finite, it has no boundary; spherical space lacks a center. In this model, the universe is described as a “3-dimensional sphere (3-sphere)” embedded in a “4-dimensional Euclidean space.” [\[1, p. 149\]](#)

In addition to the above assumptions, Einstein also assumed that time flows independently of the spatial dimensions [\[1, p. 149\]](#). He argued that this concept of time, akin to Newton's absolute time, would not contradict GTR. As a result, Einstein’s model incorporates a cosmological notion of time that all observers can agree on. In this model, where three-dimensional space is defined as spherical, the four-dimensional space-time continuum was defined by Arthur Eddington (1882-1944) as a four-dimensional cylinder embedded in a five-dimensional Euclidean space [\[10, p. 155\]](#). An object moving continuously in this universe would eventually return to its starting point, much like an object traveling on the surface of the Earth.

5. Problems of Einstein’s 1917 Universe Model

Einstein based his model on a delicate balance between cosmological constant and gravitation. However, suppose a situation arises that disturbs this balance in a slightly positive or negative way. In this scenario, there would be an imbalance between the gravitational interaction of matter and the repulsive property of the cosmological constant, causing the universe to either expand or contract. Over time,

this contraction or expansion would accelerate. Suppose, for example, that the universe shrinks slightly as a result of such an imbalance. In this case, the gravitational interaction strengthens, leading to additional contraction. This new contraction causes the gravitational interaction to become even stronger. As this contraction continues, the shrinking of the universe will accelerate and eventually this ever-shrinking universe will disappear in a singularity.

Alternatively, if the universe expands slightly due to an imbalance, the gravitational attraction would weaken, causing further expansion. This extra expansion leads to a further weakening of the gravitational interaction and a faster expansion of the universe. Over time, the expansion of the universe would continue to accelerate. It's important to note that Einstein's model is as unstable as a pencil resting on its pointed end. Such a situation is called unstable equilibrium, and Eddington showed in 1930 that Einstein's model was unstable [\[9, p. 670\]](#), a conclusion Einstein himself accepted in 1931 [\[32, p. 32\]](#).

The relatively low speed of stars compared to the speed of light was one of the key observational factors that convinced Einstein that the universe was static. He solved the GTR equations by adopting this static universe hypothesis. As a result, the equations he developed between the density of matter, the cosmological constant and the radius of curvature of the universe were based on this assumption.

In 1922, Alexander Friedmann (1888-1925) became the first to solve the GTR equations without relying on the static universe hypothesis, introducing dynamic models of the universe supported by GTR [\[14\]](#). Einstein's static universe model was merely a special case of Friedmann's more general assumptions. However, when Einstein became aware of Friedmann's paper, he initially objected, claiming the solutions contained mathematical errors, and sent a letter of complaint to the relevant journal [\[6\]](#). Ironically, it was actually Einstein who made the error. With a letter and a colleague's help, Friedmann demonstrated to Einstein that his mathematical solutions were indeed sound. Einstein eventually acknowledged his mistake and sent an apology to the journal, withdrawing his objection [\[7\]](#). This exchange also led Einstein to recognize that the GTR equations supported dynamic models of the universe. However, Einstein did not attribute any physical reality to Friedmann's solutions and

continued to reject them. Later, in 1927, Georges Lemaître (1894-1966) independently arrived at the exact dynamical solutions as Friedmann [\[25\]](#), but Einstein, still holding onto his belief in a static universe, dismissed Lemaître's work as well.

In 1912, Vesto Slipher (1875-1969) of Lowell Observatory developed a new technique for calculating the radial velocities of spiral nebulae. He applied this method to the Andromeda nebula (galaxy) and found that it was approaching the Solar System at 300 km/s [\[40\]](#). Slipher continued his research and, by 1917, determined the radial velocities of 25 spiral nebulae (galaxies), 15 of which were determined by 1915 [\[41\]](#); [\[42\]](#). Among these were nebulae (galaxies) such as NGC1068, NGC4565, and NGC4594, which were receding at a radial velocity of 1100 km/s, with an average radial velocity of 570 km/s. Slipher noted that these velocities are exceptionally high compared to normal stars, which have an average velocity of 20 km/s.

Einstein's primary objective in developing his model of the universe was to develop a logically consistent and paradox-free model that was compatible with the fundamental principles he had accepted. Notably, Einstein did not consider current astronomical data, such as the high radial velocities of spiral nebulae, and instead based his static universe model on the very slow motion of stars. In the conclusion section of his paper, Einstein made the following statements about the consistency of his model and current astronomical data:

"In any case, this view is logically consistent and the most obvious from the point of view of the general theory of relativity; whether it is tenable from the point of view of present-day astronomical knowledge will not be examined here. But in order to arrive at this non-contradictory view, we had to introduce a new extension (λ) to the gravitational field equations that is not justified by our actual knowledge of gravitation."²⁴ [\[1, p. 152\]](#)

²⁴ Translated by the author from the original text: "Jedenfalls ist diese Auffassung logisch widerspruchsfrei und vom Standpunkte der allgemeinen Relativitätstheorie die naheliegendste; ob sie, vom Standpunkt des heutigen astronomischen Wissens aus betrachtet, haltbar ist, soll hier nicht untersucht werden. Um zu dieser widerspruchsfreien Auffassung zu gelangen, mußten wir allerdings eine neue, durch unser tatsächliches Wissen von der Gravitation nicht gerechtfertigte Erweiterung der Feldgleichungen der Gravitation einführen." [\[1, p. 152\]](#)

Although Einstein did not take into account current astronomical data, Willem de Sitter (1872-1934), one of the most important astronomers of the time, challenged Einstein's model by developing an alternative GTR-based model that could explain the high redshift rates of spiral nebulae in 1917, shortly after Einstein announced his model [45]. Between 1917 and 1929, the two models competed over which one corresponded to the real universe.

In 1924, Hubble confirmed that spiral nebulae are, in fact, galaxies similar to the Milky Way. In 1927, Lemaître proposed a model of an expanding universe [25]. Inspired by de Sitter's universe model, Hubble showed in 1929, based on observational data, that there is a linear relationship between the radial velocity (redshift) and distance of galaxies [19]. These results showed that Einstein had made a mistake in thinking that the universe was static based on the slow motion of stars. To explain the universe's large-scale structure, it was necessary to consider galaxy motions, not stellar ones. Realizing this situation between 1930 and 1931, Einstein, in the spirit of the time, interpreted the new observational data as the universe expanding, abandoned the static universe assumption to which he had previously attributed physical reality, and consequently rejected the cosmological constant he had used to realize his static universe [32, pp. 10-12]. Based on these results, Einstein developed a new dynamic model of the universe in 1931 in line with the Friedmann-Lemaître solutions [32].

Although Einstein's 1917 model was abandoned, it represents an important milestone in the history of cosmology. This model symbolizes the transition from infinitely large universe models to finite and static universe models. Since the 1930s, cosmology has continued to advance through dynamical universe models. Static universe models played an intermediate role in the transition from infinite universe models to dynamic universe models and influenced the world of astronomy and cosmology from 1917 to 1929. Static universe models constitute an important part of this great struggle of humanity trying to understand the universe.

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